

Solar Sector : India Towards A Renewable Economy

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Abstract

This paper studies about what a solar energy means and how it was discovered, government schemes to boost solar power generation. It also discusses about trend showing increase in power capacity and generation, distribution amongst states and employment status in India

Further future scope and challenges faced by solar sector in India is also discussed in this paper

Keywords: Solar energy, Megawatts, Future Scope, Challenges.

Introduction

Every energy generation and transmission method affect the environment. As it is obvious conventional generating options can damage air, climate, water, land and wildlife, landscape, as well as raise the levels of harmful radiation. Renewable technologies are substantially safer offering a solution to many environmental and social problems associated with fossil and nuclear fuels. Solar energy technologies (SETs) provide obvious environmental advantages in comparison to the conventional energy sources, thus contributing to the sustainable development of human activities. Not counting the depletion of the exhausted natural resources, their main advantage is related to the reduced CO₂ emissions, and, normally, absence of any air emissions or waste products during their operation.

Solar energy is the most convenient source of renewable energy today and the coming century. The adverse effect of burning conventional hydrocarbons are eminent through global warming and health effects in many forms, including factors aggravating cancer and other illnesses. The enormous volume of fossil fuel was extracted from the ground through the years and with its finite source. Its supply will diminish and by the time it happens, it will become one of the worst crises in the history of man on a worldwide scale.

Solar energy is the most abundant stream of energy. It is available directly as solar isolation and indirectly as wind energy. Sun sends out energy in the form of electromagnetic radiation. Its potential is 178 Billion MW, which is about 20,000 times the world's demand.

The increasing demand for energy, the continuous reduction in existing sources of fossil fuels and the growing concern regarding environment pollution, have pushed mankind to explore new technologies for the production of electrical energy using clean, renewable sources, such as solar energy, wind energy, etc. Among the nonconventional, renewable energy sources, solar energy affords great potential for conversion into

electric power, able to ensure an important part of the electrical energy needs of the planet. Solar energy is free, practically inexhaustible and involves no polluting residues or green gases emissions.

This paper discusses about how solar energy works, its discovery, growth in capacity and generation of solar power in India, employment generation, different government schemes state-wise capacity holding, future scope and challenges of solar sector in India.

Objectives:

1. To study about the Solar Energy and its mechanism.
2. To study about how and when solar energy was discovered.
3. To study the trend of solar energy capacity and generation for the period of 2013-2022 in India.
4. To study different government schemes launched to boost solar power in India.
5. To study distribution of solar energy capacity amongst states of India as on 2022.
6. To study about pros of solar energy.
7. To study employment generated by solar sector by 2022.
8. To study about future scope of solar sector in India.
9. To study challenges faced by solar sector.

Review of Literature

Ehsanul Kabir et.al (2018): "Solar energy: potential and future prospects". In this article the merits and demerits of solar energy technologies are both discussed. A number of technical problems affecting renewable energy research are also highlighted, along with beneficial interactions between regulation policy frame works and their future prospects. For that they provide a global scenario with regard to solar energy technologies in terms of their potential, present capacity, prospects, limitations and policies. This was help them to expand their understanding on how much further they can count on solar energy to meet the future energy demand. Finally, they concluded that despite a few drawbacks solar energy technology is of the

most promising renewable energy sources to meet the future global energy demand.

Suhas bannur (2018): “Concentrated solar power in India: current status, challenges and future outlook”. In this article, some of the challenges that have inhibited the growth concentrated solar power are identified and possible solutions suggested. The critical challenges for CSP are related to the lack of reliable direct normal irradiance database, indigenous manufacturing and competition from PV. The results of this study carried out to assess the impact of indigenous manufacturing and economics of scale on capital costs and normalised cost of electricity are presented and this study also shows that even with indigenous manufacturing and considering economics of scale, the capital cost per megawatt of installed capacity is higher than the central electricity regulatory commission benchmark costs.

Mohd Rizwan et.al (2017): “A review paper on electricity generation from solar energy”. In this article authors reviewed about the solar energy from sunlight and discussed about their future trends and aspects. They also try to discussed working, solar panel types; emphasize the various applications and methods to promote the benefits of solar energy. And authors concluded it has more benefits compared to other forms of energy like fossil fuels and petroleum deposits. It is an alternative which is promise and consistent to meet the high energy demand. Research on solar cell and solar energy is promise has future worldwide.

P. Nagalakshmi et.al (2013): “Efficient energy management system with solar energy”. In this paper introduced an efficient energy distribution system to distribute the energy generated from the renewable sources. In order to meet the current problems, the energy generated from the renewable sources to maintain it constant. It was connected to a battery and inverter. In this research they have implemented a proto type system for the ideas. The preliminary tests show that this approach is promising for real applications. They concluded the problem with this system is that to require huge inverter to store the largely variable solar energy and its maintenance. His can be overcome by constructing solar grids parallel to the existed grids by the government.

Naveen Kumar Sharma (2011): “Solar energy in India: Strategies, policies, perspectives and future potential”. In this paper, efforts have been made to summarize the availability, current status, strategies, perspectives, promotion policies, major achievements and future potential of solar energy options in India. Thus, he concluded India has a severe electricity shortage. It needs massive additions in capacity to meet the demand of its rapidly growing economy. Development of solar

energy, which is indigenous distributed and has low marginal cost of generation, can increase energy security by diversifying supply, reducing import dependence and mitigating fuel price volatility. So photovoltaic power systems will have an important share in the electricity of the future not only in India, but all over world

Research Methodology

The study is based on secondary data which has been collected through websites, newspapers, magazines, government reports, books, research papers. Charts are used to show the trend of solar energy capacity and power generation. Pure research method is applied to study the current scenario, Government Initiatives, future scope, pros and challenges of solar energy in India.

What is Solar Energy and how it works?

Solar energy is electrical or thermal energy harvested from sunlight. Solar panels contain photovoltaic (PV) cells made up of semiconductor materials (such as silicon) to absorb elemental particles from the sun called photons. When absorbed by the panel, the photons release electrons from the atoms of the semiconductor material and the flow of these electrons within the cell creates an electric current we can direct to our circuits. Solar power is a form of energy harnessed from the power and heat of the sun's rays. It is renewable, and therefore a “green” source of energy. Solar energy is radiant light and heat from the Sun that is harnessed using a range of technologies such as solar power to generate electricity, solar thermal energy (including solar water heating), and solar architecture. It is an essential source of renewable energy, and its technologies are broadly characterized as either passive solar or active solar depending on how they capture and distribute solar energy or convert it into solar power.

Solar technology can be broadly classified as –

- **Active Solar** – Active solar techniques include the use of photovoltaic systems, concentrated solar power and solar water heating to harness the energy. Active solar is directly consumed in activities such as drying clothes and warming of air.
- **Passive Solar** – Passive solar techniques include orienting a building to the Sun, selecting materials with favourable thermal mass or light-dispersing properties, and designing spaces that naturally circulate air.

When was solar power discovered?

Solar energy was used by humans as early as the **7th century B.C.** when humans used sunlight to light fires by reflecting the sun's rays onto shiny objects. Later, in **3rd century B.C.**, the Greeks and Romans harnessed solar power with mirrors to light torches for religious ceremonies.

In 1839 and at the age of just 19, French physicist Edmond Becquerel discovered the photovoltaic (PV) effect while experimenting with a cell made of metal electrodes in a conducting solution. He noted that the cell produced more electricity when it was exposed to light – it was a photovoltaic cell.

In 1954 PV technology was born when Daryl Chapin, Calvin Fuller and Gerald Pearson developed the silicon PV cell at Bell Labs in 1954 – the first solar cell capable of absorbing

and converting enough of the sun's energy into power to run every day electrical equipment.

In the larger 20th century, commitments to utilize solar power focused on the sun's heat properties rather than electricity. The first commercial introduction of water heating systems was in California, nine years into the 20th century. It is only 64 years that they became more popular in the United States after installing a solar array in the White House by **President Jimmy Carter**.

Trend of Solar Power (Capacity and Generation) in India from 2013 to 2022

In a decade there is a tremendous growth of solar energy capacity in India from 1599 megawatts(2013) to 63146 megawatts(2022) which is almost 40 times. However Solar power capacity

is different from solar power generation, below given figures show a trend of solar power generated annually.

Along with growth in solar energy capacity, power generation by solar energy has also gone up by 30 times.

Schemes by Government of India to promote Solar Energy in the country.

1. The MNRE launched the **Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission** in 2010 to achieve 20 GW of grid connected solar power by 2022 in three phases through several steps

including **Solar Park Scheme**, Central Public Sector Undertakings (CPSUs) scheme for grid connected solar PV power projects, and Viability Gap Funding (VGF). The target was revised to 100 GW in 2014-15.

2. The Government has also launched the **Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha Uttan Mahabhiyan Yojana (PM-KUSUM)** for grid connected agricultural solar pumps.

3. **Suryamitra Skill Development Programme** by the National Institute of Solar Energy (NISE) focuses on Solar Energy project's installation, operation & maintenance.
4. **Atal Jyoti Yojana** has been launched to provide solar street lighting systems for public use.
5. Under the **Solar Transfiguration of India (SRISTI) Scheme**, financial incentives are provided to the beneficiary for installing **solar power plant rooftop projects**.
6. **Green Energy Corridor Scheme**: It is related to laying of new transmission lines and creating new sub-station capacity for evacuation (from region of production to region of consumption) of renewable power.
7. In 2014, the Government announced the '**Solar Parks and Ultra-Mega Solar Power Projects**' policy to facilitate the creation of large solar parks.

The Government has also provided financial incentives for expansion of solar energy. These include:

1. The Government has provided a **10-year tax exemption** for solar energy projects;
2. **Waiver of Inter-State Transmission System (ISTS) charges** for inter-state sale of solar and

Distribution of Solar Energy Capacity in India as on 2022

wind power for projects to be commissioned by 30th June 2025;

3. The Ministry of New and Renewable Energy provides **30% subsidy** to most solar powered items such as solar lamps and solar heating systems. It has further extended its subsidy scheme to solar-powered cold storages;
4. The Government has allowed **100% Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)** under the automatic route;
5. Government has issued orders that power shall be dispatched against Letter of Credit (LC) or advance payment to **ensure timely payment by distribution licensees to renewable energy generators**;
6. Government has also launched **Green funds** like the National Clean Energy and Environmental Fund, Green Masala Bond etc.

The Government has also undertaken initiatives for **international collaboration**. India is the founding member of the **International Solar Alliance (ISA)** which is headquartered in India. India has proposed the idea of "**One Sun, One World, One Grid**" as a means of tapping into the copious solar electricity available on a worldwide scale.

Top 5 States in Solar Power Capacity as on 2022	
STATE	CAPACITY (in Megawatts)
Rajasthan	16060 MW
Gujarat	8044 MW
Karnataka	7860 MW
Tamil Nadu	6233 MW
Telangana	4637 MW

From the above chart, we see that Rajasthan is 1st amongst state-wise distribution in solar energy capacity, followed by Gujarat and Karnataka on 2nd and 3rd position. These top 3 states hold more than 50 % of solar energy capacity in India.

Pros of Solar Energy:

Sustainability

The advantage of solar energy is that it is a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels. While fossil fuels have an expiration date that may be fast approaching, the sun is likely to be around for at least a few billion years.

Low Environmental Impact

Solar energy has a substantially reduced impact on the environment compared to fossil fuels. Its greenhouse gas emissions are inconsequential as the technology does not require any fuel combustion. Also, although concentrating solar thermal plants (CSP) are comparatively inefficient in their water usage depending on the type of technology being used, the right technology significantly increases efficiency while photovoltaic (PV) solar cells do not require any water when generating electricity.

Energy Independence

Since the sun shines across the globe, it makes every country a potential energy producer, thus allowing for greater energy independence and security. Solar energy doesn't only promise to bring security and independence at the national level; solar panels can be installed on individual homes, providing power that does not depend on being connected to a larger electrical grid.

Employment Status in the year 2022

In the year 2022, total 11,16,400 jobs were generated by solar sector which consists of 8,06,800 in Construction and Commissioning, 2,63,400 in Operation and Management, 28,600 in design and pre construction and lastly 17,600 in business development.

Solar energy can reduce your home's electricity bill

A solar energy system for your home can reduce your reliance on the grid and help you save on your electricity bill. Some owners of residential solar energy systems may even have excess power that they can sell to the utility. Instead of paying a utility for electricity, homeowners get paid by the utility. You may not have to buy an entire solar energy system to cut your home's electricity bill. Simply choose solar lights, lights that are powered by the sun instead of your home's electrical system, to help save money.

Solar power can get you money back through Solar Renewable Energy Credits (SRECs)

Some states offer solar renewable energy certificates (SREC). Each one represents a megawatt-hour of electricity generated through solar energy. Electricity suppliers buy these certificates to satisfy their state's Renewable Portfolio Standard, a requirement that a certain amount of their renewable energy come from solar. You can sell SRECs for your system's output, which is another way to earn money from your investment.

Solar panels have low maintenance costs

Solar panels are easy to maintain, as they have no moving parts that wear out over time. Just keep them clean and in good physical condition to keep them working properly. Between their low maintenance costs and average lifespan of 25 years, it can be easy to get your money's worth when investing in solar panels.

Milestones to achieve (Future Scope):

As we all know that India is a developing nation India, and it is also growing in the field of better energy infrastructure. India has about 300 days of clear and sunny weather each year, which means that India's solar energy incidence is about 5 quadrillion kilowatt-hours (kWh) per year (or 5 Wh/yr), It is estimated that the solar energy

available in India in a single year exceeds the potential energy output of all the fossil fuel reserves. Currently at 4th position among the world it has to achieve following milestones in future.

1. According to a recent report, India's solar energy capacity has grown from **6.76 GW in 2016 to an impressive 54 GW in 2022, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 41.39%**. This significant growth demonstrates India's commitment to clean energy and its potential as a leader in the global fight against climate change.
2. By 2026, Indian industry will be able to manufacture solar modules worth **100 gigawatts (GW) annually, and help the country be a net exporter of solar power**. This would significantly aid **India's target of installing 500 GW of electricity capacity from non-fossil sources by 2030**, said by Bhupinder Bhalla, Secretary, Ministry for New and Renewable Energy
3. According to studies, by **2040, India's portion of the world's total primary energy demand is expected to approximately quadruple to 11%**. In order to fulfil this enormous increase in demand while also keeping its promise to **cut its carbon footprint by 35% from 2005 levels, India will need to treble its power generation by 2030**.
4. It is expected that by **2040, around 49% of the total electricity will be generated by renewable energy** as more efficient batteries will be used to store electricity, which will **further cut the solar energy cost by 66% as compared to the current cost**. The use of renewables in place of coal will **save India Rs. 54,000 crore (US\$ 8.43 billion) annually**. Around **15,000 MW of wind-solar hybrid capacity is expected to be added between 2020-25**.
5. As per the Central Electricity Authority (CEA) estimates, by **2029-2030, the share of renewable energy generation would increase from 18% to 44%**, while that of thermal is expected to reduce from 78% to 52%. The CEA also estimates India's power requirement to grow and **reach 817 GW by 2030**.
6. India can create about **3.4 million jobs (short and long term)** by installing 280 GW solar and 140 GW wind capacity as it moves towards accomplishing its goal of 500 GW non-fossil electricity generation capacity by 2030.

What are the challenges in scaling up Solar Energy?

1. **Higher per-unit Production Costs:** Solar power costs have come down considerably but the costs of small solar power projects is higher

than other sources. The Union Government is facilitating establishment of large solar parks.

2. **Basic Challenges:** Large Solar Parks face hurdles in acquiring large tracts of land. Other challenges include high transmission and distribution losses, grid integration etc. Grid integration is a challenge due to intermittent nature of solar energy and the problem of load balancing (e.g., high load during night but non-availability of solar power at night).
3. **Environmental Issues:** Establishment of large solar parks has led to conflict with the local communities and issues in bio-diversity protection e.g., in Rajasthan and Gujarat, some projects have been halted because the transmission lines encroach upon the habitat of the critically endangered Great Indian Bustard.
4. **Slow pace of growth:** Despite significant growth in the installed solar capacity, the contribution of solar energy to the country's power generation has not grown at the same pace. The capacity expansion of rooftop solar projects has particularly low (< 20% of target by October 2022).
5. **Financial Constraints:** Residential consumers and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) who want to install solar rooftop projects face financial constraints as initial investments are generally high. A critical issue is an absence of innovative financing options offering higher sums at lower interest and longer durations.
6. **Reliance on Imports for Solar Equipment:** India at present lacks the capability to produce solar wafers or polysilicon. During the fiscal year 2021-22, India imported solar cells and modules worth about US\$ 76.62 billion from China alone. This accounted for 78.6% of India's total imports (2021-22).
7. **Waste Management:** India's solar waste is estimated to grow to 1.8 million tonnes by 2050. However, India's e-waste rules do not mandate solar cell manufacturers to recycle or dispose of waste from this sector.
8. **WTO Constraints:** India's Domestic Content Requirement (DCR) clause has faced legal challenges at the World Trade Organisation (WTO). DCR mandates the use of both solar cells and modules manufactured domestically as per specifications and testing requirements fixed by the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE)

Conclusion

Solar energy is the ultimate and best form of renewable energy. According to scientists, sunlight energy is a complete solution of present energy crisis because the amount of solar energy incident on Earth in 1 hour is equivalent to the total amount of energy consumed by humans each year.

Moreover, solar energy is extremely environment friendly because it can reduce 40 million tons of CO₂ emissions each year with the inception of solar grids that meet only 1% of electric energy demand around world. Currently, solar cells, solar power plants and solar collectors are some of the practical applications of harvesting solar energy to fulfil clean energy demand of world.

For solar energy to be considered as major renewable energy contributor, the devices used in its generation must be improved in terms of their performance because the revolutionary developments in this field are possible only if conversion, storage and utilization are done effectively. In coming years, it is expected that nanotechnology devices for solar energy harvest would be radically more effective and efficient than today and the dream of solar economy would become a reality.

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